

Articulated Soft Robots: A Feasibility Driven Control Approach

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Abstract—Soft robots offer safer interaction during tasks, but suitable controllers that leverage their uniqueness are still under development. Differential Dynamic Programming (DDP) is an effective technique for handling highly dynamic tasks with high-dimensional robots. However, the research community has focused on applying DDP to fully articulated robots while also using numerical differentiation. We present an efficient DDP-based algorithm for trajectory optimization of articulated soft robots, fully actuated or not, that jointly optimizes the states, the inputs, and the stiffness profile. We experimentally validate the approach using a fully actuated 2-DoFs compliant arm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robots often operate in unstructured environments, requiring safe and versatile interactions with humans and their surroundings. Soft robots, due to their inherent flexibility, are particularly well-suited for such tasks [1], [2], [3]. Therefore, compliant elements have been integrated at the actuation level. For instance, Series Elastic Actuators (SEAs), featuring a spring between the actuator and the load [4], and Variable Stiffness Actuators (VSAs), with a controllable stiffness, provide advantages at the cost of increased control complexity [5].

Differential Dynamic Programming (DDP) is an optimal control method that offers fast computation and is effective in systems with high Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) and multi-contact scenarios [6], [7]. We present an algorithm for efficient optimal control of articulated soft robots leveraging Feasibility-driven DDP (FDDP). The main contributions include [3]: (i) an efficient computation of the forward dynamics and Analytical Derivatives (AD) for soft articulated robots, (ii) an empirical evidence showing improved convergence and computation times with AD, and (iii) a state-feedback controller enhancing tracking performance in soft robots.

The presented approach improves accuracy and computational performance over numerical differentiation. The con-

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troller is validated with experiments on a soft robot. The code is publicly available⁴ and more details can be found in [3].

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a model for fully actuated or underactuated articulated robotic arms having SEAs or VSAs, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} M(\mathbf{q})\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) + \mathbf{K}(t)(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\theta}) &= \mathbf{0}, \\ \mathbf{B}\ddot{\boldsymbol{\theta}} + \mathbf{S}^\top \mathbf{K}(t)(\mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\theta} - \mathbf{q}) - \boldsymbol{\tau} &= \mathbf{0}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the link-side coordinates vector, $M(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the inertia matrix, and $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the vector of Coriolis, centrifugal and gravitational terms. Additionally, $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the motor-side coordinates vector, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ the motor inertia, $\mathbf{K}(t)$ the stiffness matrix, $\boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ the torque vector, and $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ the selection matrix. Finally, \dot{a} denotes the time-derivative of a .

A. Optimization problem formulation

We address soft robots’ control by formulating the following discrete-time optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\substack{\mathbf{q}_s, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_s, \\ \boldsymbol{\theta}_s, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_s, \boldsymbol{\tau}_s}} \quad & \ell_N(\mathbf{q}_N, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_N, \boldsymbol{\theta}_N, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_N) \\ & + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \int_{t_k}^{t_{k+1}} \ell_k(\mathbf{q}_k, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_k, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k, \boldsymbol{\tau}_k) dt, \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & [\mathbf{q}_{k+1}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_{k+1}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{k+1}, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{k+1}] = \boldsymbol{\psi}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}_k, \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_k, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k, \ddot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k), \\ & [\ddot{\mathbf{q}}_k, \ddot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k] = \text{FD}(\mathbf{q}_k, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_k, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k, \boldsymbol{\tau}_k), \\ & [\mathbf{q}_k, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k] \in \mathcal{Q}, [\dot{\mathbf{q}}_k, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k] \in \mathcal{V}, \boldsymbol{\tau}_k \in \mathcal{U}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{q}_k, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_k, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_k$, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_k$ are the link-side and motor-side configuration vectors, link-side and motor-side generalized velocity, and joint torques at time-step k (also called node). Conversely, ℓ_N and ℓ_k are the terminal and running cost function, $\boldsymbol{\psi}(\cdot)$ is the integrator function, while $\text{FD}(\cdot)$ represents the soft robot’s forward dynamics. Additionally, \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{V} represent the configuration and velocity space, respectively, while \mathcal{U} defines the feasible control space. Finally, $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u})$ represents the system’s dynamics, where the state vector is $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{q}^\top, \dot{\mathbf{q}}^\top, \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top, \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}^\top]$ and the inputs vector is \mathbf{u} .

III. SOLUTION APPROACH

We solve (2) using Feasibility-driven DDP. DDP tackles optimal control problems by splitting the original problem into sub-problems. It recursively solves the Bellman equation backward in time, rather than obtaining the whole trajectory

⁴https://github.com/CentroEPIaggio/aslr_to

at once. FDDP enhances classical DDP by ensuring the trajectory’s feasibility during the optimization.

Consider the Bellman equation, i.e.

$$V(\mathbf{x}_k) = \min_{\mathbf{u}_k} \ell_k(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + V_{k+1}(\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)), \quad (3)$$

where $V(\mathbf{x}_k)$ is the value function at the node k . In FDDP, the differential change is approximated by a quadratic function denoted as \mathbf{Q} . The algorithm is composed of two steps: the backward pass and the forward pass.

1) *Backward pass*: The search direction is determined by solving recursively the following

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathbf{u}_k &= \arg \min_{\delta \mathbf{u}_k} \mathbf{Q}(\delta \mathbf{x}_k, \delta \mathbf{u}_k) = \hat{\mathbf{k}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}} \delta \mathbf{x}_k, \\ \text{s.t.} \quad \underline{\mathbf{u}} &\leq \mathbf{u}_k + \delta \mathbf{u}_k \leq \bar{\mathbf{u}}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here, $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = -\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}_k}^{-1} \mathbf{Q}_{\mathbf{u}_k}$ represents the feed-forward term, $\hat{\mathbf{K}} = -\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}_k}^{-1} \mathbf{Q}_{\mathbf{x}\mathbf{u}_k}$ denotes the feedback term at time-step k , and $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}_k}$ is the input’s free subspace Hessian. The value function’s gradient and Hessian are updated using $\delta \mathbf{u}_k$.

2) *Forward pass*: After obtaining the search direction from (4), the step size α is determined through an Armijo-based line search algorithm. The input and state trajectory are then updated using α as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k &= \mathbf{u}_k + \alpha \hat{\mathbf{k}} + \hat{\mathbf{K}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k - \mathbf{x}_k), \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} &= \mathbf{f}_k(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k, \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k) - (1 - \alpha) \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{k-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$ and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k$ represent the optimal state and input vectors (with both feedback and feedforward) at node k , respectively. Without input bounds, the algorithm reduces to FDDP [6]. For further details, please refer to [8], [3].

A. Soft robots’ dynamics

Computing the forward dynamics in (1) can be achieved by differentiating τ_l and τ_m as

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_l &\triangleq -\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) - \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{S}\theta), \\ \tau_m &\triangleq -\mathbf{S}^\top \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{S}\theta - \mathbf{q}) + \dot{\tau}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Inverting the matrix analytically, as follows, avoids the computationally expensive numerical inversion of the KKT matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} \delta \ddot{\mathbf{q}} \\ \delta \ddot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \tau_l}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \\ \frac{\partial \tau_m}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \end{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{x} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \tau_l}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \\ \frac{\partial \tau_m}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \end{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{u} \right). \quad (7)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

We validate the approach using a fully actuated 2-DoFs compliant arm equipped with VSAs with encoders on both the motor and link sides. The elastic actuator’s torque τ and nonlinear stiffness σ are

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= 2\beta \cosh(\alpha\theta_s) \sinh(\alpha(q - \theta_e)), \\ \sigma &= 2\alpha\beta \cosh(\alpha\theta_s) \cosh(\alpha(q - \theta_e)), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha = 6.7328 \text{ rad}^{-2}$, $\beta = 0.0222 \text{ N m}$, θ_e is the motor’s equilibrium position, θ_s adjusts the motor stiffness, and q is the link-side position.

The first and the second joint stiffnesses are $\sigma = 5 \text{ Nm/rad}$ and 2 Nm/rad . The state, control, ℓ_k , and goal-tracking regularization weights are set to 10^{-2} , 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , and 10^{-1} , respectively.

Figure 1 shows some snapshots of the go-to-origin experiment, while fig. 2 shows the commands and the measured values. The reference and measured joint positions of the arm when controlled with only feedforward and with feedforward and feedback are reported in Figs. 2a and 2b, respectively. The feedforward inputs are shown in Fig. 2c. Finally, Tab 2d reports the joint errors with and without feedback.

Fig. 1: Snapshots of the go-to-origin task for the 2-DoFs fully actuated compliant arm.

Fig. 2: Results of the go-to-origin task.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented an efficient optimal control formulation for soft robots that builds on FDDP. We introduced a method for fast dynamics and analytical derivatives’ computation, validating it on hardware across a swing up task. A promising future direction is to extend the framework to an MPC-based solution.

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